

Fixture Layout Optimization using FEA, ANN and ABCA

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Abstract – Manufacturing industries, which are moving toward greater degrees of automation, have higher priority of development over other industries. These industries require specialized tooling to minimize the manufacturing costs. The improvement of product quality, minimization of production cost etc., can be achieved with the help of various process or machining attachments such as fixtures, tools and inspection devices. Among all the devices, fixtures play an important role in improving the quality of machining processes. The fixtures help to locate the workpiece against the cutting tool in proper orientation minimizes the workpiece elastic deformation and helps to improve the machining accuracy. In this research paper, a two-dimensional (2D) workpiece deformation model is developed using results of FEA and the fixturing elements positions are optimized using artificial bee colony algorithm (ABCA) to minimize workpiece elastic deformation.

Keywords: Workpiece Elastic Deformation, Fixture Layout Optimization, ABCA

I. Introduction

In manufacturing, the mobility of workpiece should be reduced to achieve maximum accuracy. The workpiece need to be held securely against the cutting tool to reduce dimensional and form errors. Fixturing elements like the locators and clamps are used to hold the workpiece to constrain any movement. The positions of the locators and clamps are the influencing parameters in the workpiece deformation and thereby leads to the machining errors.

Krishnakumar & Melkote [1] and Kaya [2] developed a workpiece elastic model and used GA to optimize the fixture layout for minimizing the workpiece elastic deformation under static loading conditions. Krishnakumar & Melkote [1], Siebenaler [3], and Kaya [2] developed a fixture-workpiece model, and the influences of compliance of the fixture elements on deformation of the workpiece were analysed using finite element analysis (FEA) software-ANSYS and a built-in finite element solver. Prabhakaran et al. [4] and Padmanaban & Prabhakaran [5] used GA for optimizing the fixture layout under static and dynamic conditions respectively. Prabhakaran et al. [4] were minimized the the fixture layout to reduce the dimensional and form errors. FEM was used to determine the workpiece deformation. The optimization methods ACA and GA were used to optimize the layout and optimized layouts are determined separately.

In this research paper, 2D workpiece deformation model has been developed and simulated using FEA under the support of fixturing elements. To determine the

work piece elastic deformation in the fixture layout, the FEA based empirical model is developed using artificial neural network (ANN). The optimization of the fixture layout under static conditions has been achieved through ABCA..

II. Workpiece Model

2D workpiece geometry [1] for static analysis has been considered as shown in fig.1. The milling operation is carried out to make a slot in the workpiece geometry. The machining force is acting through the area as shown in fig.2. The Young's Modulus (E) = 2.1×10^5 N/mm² and Poisson's ratio (ν) = 0.3. The machining forces applied are: $F_X = 100$ N and $F_Y = 286$ N. The clamping forces considered are Clamp 1= 350N and Clamp 2=200N.

Fig.1 Workpiece Geometry

The workpiece elastic deformation which is the objective function is dependent on the range of distance defined for each fixturing element. The range of distance defined for each fixturing element used is given in Table1.

Fig.2 Position of Fixturing Elements

TABLE I
RANGE OF FIXTURING ELEMENTS

Fixturing element	Range of distance (mm)
Locator 1	L1 = 5 – 145
Locator 2	L2 = 5 – 145
Locator 3	L3 = 5 – 85
Clamp 1	C1 = 5 – 125
Clamp 2	C2 = 5 – 65

III. Optimization of Workpiece Fixture Layout

III.1. Carbon Monoxide Emission

Finite element analysis is used to solve various engineering problems such as deformation analysis, heat flow analysis, fluid flow analysis etc. The 2D fixture-workpiece system considered is modeled using FEA software ANSYS version 13. The workpiece is modeled using SOLID 185 element and meshed with tetrahedral configuration. The positions of the locators and clamps are varied within the specified range mentioned and the elastic deformation in the workpiece is determined for fixture layouts of different sets using FEA. The meshed finite element workpiece model is shown in fig.3.

Fig. 3 Finite element workpiece model

III.2. Empirical Model using Artificial Neural Network

ANN has been used to develop the model for workpiece elastic deformation for the various fixture layouts. The network parameters such as number of layers, number of neurons in the hidden layers, number of training iterations, learning rate and momentum factor

are decided upon to enhance the speed and efficiency of learning to predict the response.

TABLE II
NETWORK PARAMETERS

Parameter	Description
Learning rule adopted	Back
Number of neurons in the input layer	5
Number of neurons in the output	1
Number of hidden layer	1
Number of neurons in the hidden	10
Activation function	tansig, tansig,
Acceptable mean-squared error	0.00000001
Learning Rate	0.65
Momentum factor	0.85

In the design of network architecture, the number of hidden layers and the number of simulated neurons within each layer and their transfer functions are verified by trial and error to improve the performance of a neural network. The network parameters decided are shown in Table 2.

III.3. Optimization using ABCA

The ABCA is an optimization algorithm based on the intelligent behaviour of honey bee swarm (Karaboga [6]). The information exchange between the bees is considered as the theme for the occurrence in the development of the collective knowledge.

The bees colony considered here consists of employed bees, onlooker bees and scouts. An employed bee goes to a food source and the number of employed bees is equal to the number of food sources. The information about the food sources are obtained by the onlooker bees from the employed bees. Scouts randomly search for new food sources around the hive. The employed bee dances in the hive after finding the food source and evaluating its nectar amount. The duration of the dance is proportional to the quality of the food source. The onlooker bee selects a food source and becomes employed. The probability of selection of the food source depends on the dancing duration.

In the ABCA based fixture layout optimization, the value of the objective function which is the workpiece elastic deformation is calculated using the empirical model developed by ANN. The position of the fixturing elements is represented by the position of food source and the fitness of the fixture layout is represented by the nectar amount of food source. The number of employed bees is equal to the number of solutions in the population of fixture layout design. If the termination condition is met, the search process is stopped and the best positional values of all the fixturing elements are reported.

Each set of variables considered in every iteration is simulated and the least workpiece elastic deformation is found out. The control parameters for ABCA are tabulated in Table 3.

Parameter	Range
Initial Population	20
Crossover Probability (P_c)	0.65-
No. of Iterations	0.85 50

The least workpiece elastic deformation is obtained for each crossover probability and the results of the ABCA runs for the different crossover probabilities P_c are shown in Fig.4- Fig.8.

Fig. 4 ABCA Run with $P_c=0.65$

Fig.5 ABCA Run with $P_c=0.7$

Fig.6 ABCA Run with $P_c=0.75$

Fig.7 ABCA Run with $P_c=0.8$

Fig.8 ABCA Run with $P_c=0.85$

The results of workpiece elastic deformation for different crossover probabilities are obtained and analysed based on the rate of convergence in each iteration. From the obtained results, It is found that the ABCA process with the crossover probability (P_c) of 0.65 has converged to the least workpiece elastic deformation of 0.020687mm.

IV. Conclusion

In this paper, 2D workpiece geometry has been considered for optimizing the workpiece-fixture layout system. A set of fixture layout parameters were considered and the workpiece model has been developed using FEA. The FEA model were simulated to obtain the deformation results of the various fixture layouts. Based on the developed FEA model and the respective results of FEA simulation, the empirical model has been developed using ANN. The empirical model is considered for calculating the objective function (deformation) for the various fixture layouts. To determine the optimum layout, with least deformation, for the 2D fixture the heuristic optimization technique ABCA is used.

The ANN is found to be opt method for the prediction of the fixture layout deformation as the ANN results obtained are very closer to the results of the FEA model. The ABCA optimization method is able provide the optimized fixture layout parameters with least fixture deformation. The results of the ABCA are simulated using the FEA model and the results compared. The results are found to be closer.

Further, the FEA model can be extended for the 3D fixture with an increase in the number of locaters and objective function of deformation. The results will be used to develop an empirical model and optimized for the fixture layout parameters.

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